

RISK MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF USING INFORMATION MODELING TECHNOLOGIES FOR CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS

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Abstract

Risks are inevitable in any construction project. To eliminate or mitigate their consequences, risk management methodology is applied in construction project management. In recent years, the likelihood of a risk event has increased in the architecture and construction industries due to increased structural complexity, the scope of construction work, and the use of new and complex construction methods. However, existing risk management practices have shown limited practical impact on the development of systematic risk management within construction projects. To address this issue, information modeling (IM) technologies play an important role in risk management at the design, construction, and maintenance stages of a construction project. Based on information technology, risk management can be integrated with modern IT processes for construction project management. Since the implementation of IM in risk management on construction projects remains limited, it is necessary to develop a IM implementation system to eliminate risks throughout the entire lifecycle of a construction project. This article examines the application of IM in risk management for construction projects at various stages of the project lifecycle.

The recommendations provided illustrate the use of risk management systems (RMS) in risk identification, risk response, and risk monitoring. Research shows that one of the most significant problems is the lack of a framework aligning RMS with risk management during project development and implementation. The development of such a framework encompasses a risk mitigation model, risk management cycles, and a flexible risk management structure across all stages of the construction project lifecycle.

Keywords: information modeling technologies (IMT), integration of IMT and risk management, construction.

Introduction

A construction project begins with the design phase, then goes through a lengthy construction phase, and finally an operational period lasting until complete depreciation and demolition. Consequently, various risks are present at all stages of the project's lifecycle. This means that, regardless of the type of activity, there is always a possibility of risky situations and impacts on the project, to varying degrees depending on the type of risk and the severity of the consequences. Risks manifest themselves in damage to structures, injuries or fatalities on-site, budget overruns, construction schedule delays, and so on.

In recent years, with the rapid development of urban infrastructure, risks have increased due to the increasing complexity and scale of projects and the use of innovative technologies and construction methods. Consequently, all participants in the investment and construction process must participate in risk management throughout the project's lifecycle to ensure its safe and sustainable completion. Risk management is a log-

ical and systematic approach that includes a set of activities and processes to facilitate the exchange of information regarding the identification, analysis, assessment, and treatment of risks, as well as the reporting of achieved results.

The first and most important step in the risk management process is the early identification of potential risks. Based on this analysis, the likelihood of occurrence and the significance of the identified risks are then determined. To avoid serious accidents and improve the effectiveness of risk management in construction projects, various risk assessment methods are used in practice, such as fault tree analysis, decision trees, and neural networks (NN). These are divided into two categories: qualitative and quantitative risk analysis. However, it should be noted that these are primarily traditional methods, heavily dependent on the knowledge base and experience of managers.

In recent years, the development and application of construction information models has become one of the areas that will play a significant role in risk management during the design, construction, and operation

of facilities. IMTs are defined as "an object-oriented parametric three-dimensional model that digitally represents the physical, functional, and other characteristics of an object (or its individual parts) as a set of information-rich elements" [1]. A number of software applications are being used to support the practical use of IMTs, and IMT-related digital tools have also emerged to improve safety and risk management, such as replacing traditional 2D design methods with 3D modeling using automated verification tools built on IMTs to prevent traffic accidents on construction sites.

Currently, IMT platforms exist that can be applied to facility design for various purposes. However, integrating IMTs and risk management for construction projects remains a complex task.

Trends in the application of information modeling technologies for risk management in construction projects

The fundamental concept of risk mitigation is that the greatest opportunities for identifying and mitigating risks should be realized as early as possible during the design and planning stages, while residual risks should be managed during the construction and operation of the facility. Decision makers must establish an effective communication environment, clearly identify and analyze risks, implement measures to control them, and record and properly report the results. Typically, the project coordinator is responsible for monitoring, controlling, and managing the entire process, as well as ensuring effective operation throughout the project lifecycle. However, at each stage, responsibilities for risk management are identified.

Specifically, during the planning and design stage, the general designer is responsible for risk management and for collaborating with other project participants to identify all foreseeable risks that may arise during the lifecycle. During the construction phase, the general contractor is responsible for managing risks on the construction site to ensure the safe completion of the project within budget and on time. After the facility is handed over to the client (or operating organization) for daily maintenance and operational risk management.

However, there are some unresolved issues in the current risk management system for construction projects. For example, failure to identify potential project-related risks at the first stage of the risk management process can lead to new risks. Since the project goes through various stages and most participants complete their work during these stages, unidentified risks can lead to a "spillover effect" and the likelihood of risk events may increase.

Therefore, maintaining and applying a knowledge base acquired at each stage of the construction project, as well as collecting the necessary data are key prerequisites for successful risk management.

Another issue is that risk management in construction projects is a voluntary requirement. As projects progress, any common risks must be identified and addressed, and the relevant information documented. Sometimes this work can be ignored or forgotten. As a project moves from the designer to the contractor and then to the developer, large volumes of risk information can be lost if improperly recorded.

To overcome existing problems in traditional risk management, information modeling technologies have proven to be an effective way to facilitate early risk identification and assessment in design and construction through 3D visualization, 4D planning, and 5D cost estimating [3].

With the development of information modeling technologies, approaches to risk identification and analysis have been developed. The growing interest in the application of information modeling technologies in the risk management process is currently being explained by a number of factors.

First, the adopted general construction development strategy promotes the implementation of information modeling technologies in the construction industry. Secondly, risk management based on information modeling technologies allows construction companies to take advantage of the technology's technical advantages in early risk identification. For example, it becomes easier to identify errors and verify structures in 3D, and information modeling technologies, where parametric information is linked to objects, are convenient for any optimization and modifications [6].

Thirdly, large-scale construction projects, which involve a large number of multidisciplinary specialists, are complex to manage. Effective communication is always required for successful risk management. Information modeling technologies can

- 1) facilitate the creation of a communication environment that allows for an accurate understanding of the nature and needs of the project;
- 2) design, develop, and analyze the project;
- 3) manage the construction of the facility; and
- 4) manage the completed facility during its operation and decommissioning [5].

Integration of information modeling technology tools and the risk management process for construction projects

The integration of information modeling and the risk management process should proceed through several stages to ensure maximum alignment of information modeling capabilities with the risk management process.

1. The first stage involves defining the characteristics of project risk events, which are presented in the form of a corresponding catalog, indicating the risk code, risk type (e.g., external), risk impact area (e.g., legal, construction), the location of the risk event in the project life cycle (e.g., construction site, structures), and risk factors (e.g., insufficient project analysis or problems with utility networks). Next, a catalog of applicable risk management tools (RMT) is compiled, specifying the codes, the use of the RMT (e.g., for a construction site), a description (e.g., the use of a RMT in which geographic information system (GIS) tools are used in conjunction with software to determine the optimal location of a facility), the expected benefit (e.g., assessing an existing or potential facility in connection with a development program; savings on utility costs), information (e.g., site information—natural slope, road proximity, land use/coverage, land value, geological information), information source (e.g., owner, project en-

gineer), tools (e.g., software development, GIS software), and the model/results (e.g., an analytical model of the construction site). The catalogs can be expanded by adding both new risks and new RMT.

2. In the second stage, a risk analysis must be conducted to demonstrate the relationship between risks and the corresponding RMT by comparing the characteristics of each risk and the types of RMT. For this purpose, risk catalogs and IMTs are reviewed. Since each risk implies a specific information modeling technology application, a clear selection process is necessary to select the appropriate information modeling technology.

3. In the third stage, a final risk-IMT application catalog must be created. This catalog must specify the risk event, the risk impact area, the risk factor (e.g., incomplete project analysis), the simplified risk factor (e.g., verification), and the primary objective/sub-objective (e.g., conclusion/control). The relationships between risks and the characteristics of the IMTs used are determined based on the risk factors and the objectives of the IMT use [4]. Two types of classification of the IMTs used can be applied: based on the asset life cycle and the list of objectives for the IMT use.

Since not all IMTs are suitable for managing a particular risk, selection is necessary based on the risk characteristics and IMT. The main selection factors are the objectives for the IMT use, the asset life cycle, and the project elements. Targeted selection of IMTs is conducted using the risk-IMT catalog. Selection based on the asset life cycle (ALC) factor involves selecting IMTs based on the risk occurrence time. Selection based on the project element factor focuses on those elements where the risk arises.

Due to the complexity and variability of construction projects, risk distribution may vary, and adjustments to the IMT selection results may be required.

Despite some advances in risk management based on information modeling technologies, most practical efforts are focused on the design and construction phases of a project. Furthermore, it should be noted that due to technical limitations and the lack of human factors testing, most of these technologies are still at the conceptual stage and have not been widely used in real-world practice. Much of the development concerns new digital technologies for managing specific risks, such as predicting and preventing traffic accidents. Furthermore, traditional risk management methods and processes still play an important role in real-world projects. Clearly, future research will align information modeling technologies with traditional risk management methods in specific construction projects.

Overall, there remains a gap in the application of information modeling technologies for risk management on construction sites. Information modeling technologies will drive the development of the architectural, design, and survey industry (ADSI), making risk management more effective than it is today. Risk management will play a significant role when key construction project stakeholders begin to utilize these technologies in their daily work. However, little research currently focuses on how new and traditional risk management methods, activities, and processes can be

integrated most effectively to make information modeling-based risk management more applicable in the ADS industry.

The information modeling technologies selected for each risk can be presented in tabular form (table). The application of information modeling technologies is distributed across all stages of the facility life cycle (FLC): the architectural and construction design (ACD) stage (including engineering surveys), the pre-construction stage (PC), the construction stage (C), the facility operation stage (O), and the facility disposal stage. For example, a technological risk may be identified at a construction site, and this risk is associated with specific information modeling technologies used to manage it—information modeling technologies 1 (Modeling Existing Conditions), information modeling technologies 3 (Visualization), and information modeling technologies 4 (Database Information Management)—which can be implemented to manage this risk throughout the project lifecycle.

While the matrix shows the appropriate information modeling technologies for risk management, it does not describe how to apply each information modeling technology in the risk management process. This requires the preparation of a separate guide with more detailed information on the use of information modeling technologies in risk management.

Risk management tasks for construction projects based on information modeling technologies

The proposed approach can be applied in two different scenarios. First, when risks or applicable IMTs are defined in the catalogs. Second, when risks or IMTs are not included in the catalogs and new risks and/or IMTs need to be added. The first scenario corresponds to a situation where the project planning team is satisfied that the catalogs are sufficient to characterize the project environment. In this scenario, the software can begin with risk exploration. If new risks and/or IMTs need to be added to the catalogs, the application must begin with data configuration.

Two user groups are defined. The first are risk and IMT experts, and the second are project clients and contractors. Since the adopted database structure is flexible enough to accommodate user modifications, new risks and IMTs can be added to the database in accordance with various project requirements and new IMTs. Risk and IMT experts can also review risk and IMT characteristics depending on their level of expertise. This includes database adjustments and an analysis of the IMT use objectives. The second group of users is more focused on applying the risk management process to the project.

If we consider the critical risks identified through classification (e.g., design changes, deficiencies in specifications and drawings, construction failures, and subcontractor performance), the goal of risk management will be primarily to reduce losses due to their impacts related to design, as well as to eliminate any construction conflicts, starting from the design stage, as they can lead to increased costs during construction.

Risk management measures should focus on the most important risks: poor workmanship and the need

to address it, equipment and material availability issues, safety/accidents, supplier/subcontractor problems due to low productivity, construction failures, inconsistencies between design and construction work, and exceptionally unfavorable climatic conditions.

This risk management approach depends largely on the experience and knowledge of specialists and the degree to which the problems to be solved are identified. There are limitations to the application of IMT if the company is a contractor and is guided by the client's requirements when applying IMT. In this situation, it is important for the contractor to maximize the use of IMT in risk management.

If the company operates at the operational stage of a facility, it is recommended to use IMT for the following purposes: infrastructure asset management: (1) record modeling, (2) disaster planning, (3) facilities monitoring and management, (4) infrastructure management, (5) building condition analysis, and (6) building maintenance planning.

Construction companies still lack sufficient information regarding the concept underlying the improved processes that IMT can offer. Another issue is that the decision to implement IMT depends on the scale of the construction project. Another important issue is that IMT implementation requires significant upfront costs. However, some employers would prefer to use more labor than invest in IMT.

Conclusion

Based on the research conducted in this article, it has been established that the link between project risks and the use of risk management tools remains insufficient. One potential direction for this research is to explore the methodology for using risk management tools in risk management. The implementation of risk management tools should not encounter common barriers such as a shortage of qualified experts or significant investment costs. Proposals are formulated for the application of existing and potential use of risk management tools.

A conceptual approach to integrating risk management tools into the risk management process is proposed. Within the overall risk management framework, a risk mitigation model is developed, linked to all stages of the investment and construction process: the architectural and construction design stage (including engineering surveys), the pre-construction stage, the construction stage, the facility operation stage, and the facility disposal stage.

A risk management cycle (identification, analysis, assessment, impact mitigation) is developed at each stage. This makes it possible to integrate cycle-based business processes into the risk management functions performed in structural units. At each stage of the project, the coordinator creates a flexible risk management service structure. This approach will expand the application of the IMT not only for risk identification and analysis, but also for decision-making.

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